

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

Modern education system is not merely concerned with giving formal knowledge, rather it aims at the complete development of the personality of an individual. It provides him with all-round development so that he becomes capable to face any challenges in life and also harnesses inner potential for social betterment. The objective of modern education is to support a student to acquire human values, scientific attitude and noble character. Such an education system helps in transforming society by producing upright citizens who can contribute positively towards national progress. The curriculum should be designed in such a manner that students are able to face practical problems which they come across in day-to-day life. So in this situation critical and creative thinking abilities of the students need to improved for their future development. Creativity has led to innovations, discoveries and inventions that have made the learners, and students lives comfortable. Creative thinking can help them to improve problem solving skills, boost their confidence, freedom their thought, develop leadership skills, and also quality of life.

Keywords: creative thinking, thinking skills and abilities, convergent and divergent thinking, quality of ideas.

Introduction: In recent years there has been an increasing recognition that creativity and creative thinking should be fostered as valued outcomes of schooling, either in their own right, or as part of a set of so-called '21st-century skills' (Partnership for 21st Century Skills 2009; Griffin & Care, 2012; Kereluik et al., 2013; Adams, et al., 2015). While the importance of creative thinking is now widely accepted, it remains the case that there is a lack of agreement regarding a definition of creative thinking.

According to modern education approach research is necessary when solving a problem. But there are situations where a problem's specific cause is difficult to pinpoint. This can occur when there's not enough time to narrow down the problem's source or there are differing opinions about its root cause. In such cases, students can use creative problem-solving, which allows you to explore potential solutions regardless of whether a problem has been defined. Creative problem-solving encourages exploring open-ended solutions. It also focuses on developing new perspectives and fostering creativity in the education system.

Literature review: The assessment of creativity and creative thinking has typically been characterised in relation to the '4Ps' first identified in the 1960s (Rhodes, 1961). These 'Ps' are:

- the person (personality features and dispositions of an individual),
- the process (the observable learning and thinking involved in a creative act),
- product (the end result), and
- press (the environment, including social factors).

Researchers have tended to focus on one, at most, two of these aspects, and in doing so, align themselves with a particular research tradition, and manner of conceiving of creative thinking. ACER's (Australian

Council of Educational Research) model has a focus on the process of creative thinking, and the end product, with the knowledge that these features are observable and amenable to being measured using new techniques for standardised assessments that can be easily administered in the classroom. In addition to having a different focus from some of the other frameworks reviewed, ACER's construct of creative thinking attempts to overcome the shortcomings of previous frameworks, most notably that they do not contain a sufficiently elaborated definition of creative thinking, or, where critical and creative thinking are combined, there is insufficient emphasis on the latter (Victorian Curriculum and Assessment Authority, 2018). According to the authors creative thinking is defined as:

"the capacity to generate many different kinds of ideas, manipulate ideas in unusual ways and make unconventional connections in order to outline novel possibilities that have the potential to elegantly meet a given purpose".

An important aspect of thinking is to be able to think creatively (Beghetto & Kaufman, 2010; Sternberg, 2009, 2010a,b). Creativity is the ability to think about something in novel and unusual ways and come up with unique solutions to problems.

J. P. Guilford (1967) distinguished between **convergent thinking**, which produces one correct answer and is characteristic of the kind of thinking required on conventional intelligence tests, and **divergent thinking**, which produces many

answers to the same question and is more characteristic of creativity. For example,

a typical convergent item on a conventional intelligence test is, "How many quarters will you get in return for 60 dimes?" The question has only one right answer. In contrast, divergent questions have many possible answers. For example, consider these questions:

“What image comes to mind when you sit alone in a dark room?” and “What are some unique uses for a paper clip?” Are intelligence and creativity related? Although most creative students are quite intelligent (as measured by high scores on conventional intelligence

tests), in other respects the reverse is not necessarily true. Many highly intelligent students are not very creative (Kaufman & Sternberg, 2010a,b; Sternberg, 2009, 2010c).

Figure 1. Creative thinking framework:

What is the generation of ideas?

Creative thinking is, at its core, a generative process. This strand acknowledges the importance of the production of many different ideas, sometimes called ideational fluency (Guilford, 1950) to the process of creative thinking. When a large number of ideas are produced, one or more could be combined to construct a creative product. While some researchers have argued that generation of ideas may be a domain-specific, rather than domain general aspect of creative thinking (e.g. Han, 2003), it is likely to be possible to improve this issue by assessing creative thinking within more than one domain.

The notion that if a greater number of ideas is produced it is more likely that a creative one will be among them relies on the belief that distinct ideas will be produced. If many ideas are produced, but they share fundamental similarities, it is likely that the level of creative thinking exhibited by each idea will be similar. Likewise, if a number of similar ideas is produced, it is less likely that they will be combined or synthesised to form a new idea or solution. This aspect explicitly addresses the number of distinct ideas presented.

What is experimentation?

A key element of creative thinking is the ability to ‘play’ with ideas, both previously existing, and newly-generated. Critical to this process are the ability to consciously consider ideas from multiple perspectives, and to think creatively within the constraints of a task. This can lead to ‘new’ ideas in the form of processes such as adaptation and synthesis (Lassig, 2013).

Creative thinking necessarily occurs within the constraints imposed in order to meet the purpose of the task. A challenge of creative thinking is to think flexibly enough to find novel ways to move within the constraints. However, we often constrain ourselves more than necessary. Creative thinkers consciously shift their own perspective of a problem in order to redefine the problem’s context, and therefore come up with new ways to approach attempts to find a solution

While other skills such as critical thinking and collaboration each also contain a notion of acknowledging other perspectives, this is generally in relation to identifying and addressing gaps in knowledge. In creative thinking, however, the ability to be flexible and see things from a different perspective is about seeing information that is already known, in new ways. In order to think creatively, learners need to learn how to push the boundaries of a task to maximise the amount of creative thinking space. Conscious shifts in perspective can allow us to identify what aspects of a task can be changed.

Manipulating ideas requires flexible thinking. Creative thinkers know how to manipulate the elements of a task or prompt in different ways to generate new ideas. They combine, subvert, twist or graft elements together in unlikely ways to open up new possibilities and radically different ways of thinking about something. The inclusion of this aspect is an clear acknowledgment that creative thinking often involves adaptation or synthesis of existing ideas, rather than the generation of entirely new ones, a notion which is well-supported by research (e.g. Lassig, 2013).

What is quality of ideas?

Creative thinking does not exist in a vacuum. This aspect is about ensuring that the ideas generated are of high quality. Examining the appropriateness (or otherwise) of a solution is an idea that is present in most of the frameworks reviewed. A strength of the ACER approach is that not only is the importance of the solution as a creative product acknowledged, but the key features of a product that demonstrates creative thinking are specified. The idea that a creative product must be new is also fundamental to existing definitions of creativity (Plucker et al., 2004; Sternberg & Lubart, 1999). In the context of educational assessment, this key aspect remains important, but qualification is necessary. It is unlikely that students will generate an idea that is truly new, in the sense of it never having been generated before. As Smith and Smith (2010) have noted, however, an idea that is new to a student, even if not new in an absolute sense, can still be considered creative. Supporting creative thinking for young students will usually involve providing opportunities for experimentation and risk-taking with the teacher modelling the explicit valuing of unusual responses.

Elaboration of an idea is about illustrating the richness of its potential to meet a given purpose. It may require providing detail when an idea might initially seem far-fetched in order to explain how it could potentially be effective. Elaboration gives substance to an idea, and acts to support its fitness for purpose. While the level of detail in a response has not tended to be included in more recent frameworks, its importance was acknowledged in early work, with elaboration included as one of the response measures in the influential work of Guilford (1950)

Steps in the Creative Process

The creative process is often described as a five-step sequence:

1. *Preparation.* Students become immersed in a problem issue that interests them and their curiosity is aroused.
2. *Incubation.* Students churn ideas around in their head, a point at which they are likely to make some unusual connections in their thinking.
3. *Insight.* Students experience the “Aha!” moment when all pieces of the puzzle seem to fit together.
4. *Evaluation.* Now students must decide whether the idea is valuable and worth pursuing. They need to think, “Is the idea novel or is it obvious?”
5. *Elaboration.* This final step often covers the longest span of time and involves the hardest work. This step is what famous twentieth-century American inventor

Thomas Edison was thinking about when he said that creativity is 1 percent inspiration and 99 percent perspiration. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi (1996) argues that this five-step sequence provides a helpful framework for thinking about how to develop creative ideas. However, he emphasizes that creative people don't always go through the steps in a linear sequence. For example, elaboration is often interrupted by periods of incubation. Fresh insights may appear during incubation, evaluation, and elaboration. And insight might take years or only a few hours. Sometimes the creative idea consists of one deep insight. At other times, it is a series of small insights.

Conclusion: As far as the usefulness of modern education is concerned it can be summarized as follows: Firstly, modern education widens the intellect of a student by introducing new methods and objective psychology, which enables him to face different situations with confidence. Moreover it helps in developing analytical skills among students so that they can understand complex issues easily. This ultimately results in making good decision-makers who can contribute positively towards social growth.

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